

Relation Between Hypertensive Retinopathy with Left Ventricular Hypertrophy and Proteinuria in Hypertensive Patient

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Abstract

Background: Hypertensive retinopathy is almost always associated with other target organ damage. Relationship of hypertensive retinopathy with left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) and proteinuria was inconclusive in previous studies.

Objective: To assess the relation between Left Ventricular Hypertrophy and Proteinuria in Hypertensive Patient with Retinopathy in Tertiary Care Hospital.

Methods: This is a cross-sectional observational study and conducted at the Department of Medicine and Cardiology in Dhaka Medical College Hospital. Total 100 hypertensive retinopathy patients were included in the study. Following informed written consent, physical examination, relevant investigations were done. In all cases, Ethical issues were maintained properly and collected data were analysed by SPSS 20.

Results: Among 100 participants, mean age was 57.15 (± 12.989 SD) years [age range 29-85] and 61% were male & 39% were female. Mean value of Systolic (SBP) and Diastolic Blood pressure (DBP) in Grade (G)-1, G-2 and G-3 hypertension were 150.8 (± 5.4) & 94 (± 2.6) mm Hg, 170.3 ± 4.9 & 101.0 ± 4.7 mm Hg and 188.0 ± 7.0 & 102.6 ± 6.5 mm Hg respectively and it is significantly associated with severity of LVH (p value < 0.001 in both SBP & DBP). Proteinuria is also associated with severity of hypertension ($p < 0.001$) but there were no association of Hypertensive retinopathy with LVH and proteinuria (p value 0.32 and 0.27 respectively).

Conclusion: LVH & Proteinuria is associated with severity of Hypertension but Hypertensive retinopathy is not associated with LVH and proteinuria, though further large cohort is recommended for final comment.

More Information

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Introduction

Systemic hypertension is a major public health concern that affects more than one billion people around the Globe [1]. It has been reported that estimated number of adults with hypertension in 2000 is 972 million worldwide and developing countries outweighed that of developed countries by almost twofold (639 million in developing countries versus 333 million in developed countries [2]. And it is also predicted that the burden of hypertension would increase to approximately 1.56 billion in the year 2025 [3]. In India the prevalence rate is 28.4% which is almost similar prevalence in

Bangladesh (26.4% adults), of them 20.3% is male and 32.4% is female [3-5].

Hypertension (HTN) can occur due to primary (essential) or secondary cause [6]. However, underlying mechanism of essential hypertension is still remains incompletely understood. Several factors seems to be responsible and among them interplay between environmental and genetic factors were considered major contributors [7]. Moreover, lifestyle-related factors, metabolic syndrome, angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) gene polymorphism appear to be important contributor to hypertension [8]. Although hypertension is often asymptomatic, the disease is

related to different types of target organ damage (TOD) and associated clinical conditions [9]. Subtle TOD, such as left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), retinopathy, microalbuminuria and cognitive dysfunction, occurs early in the course of hypertensive disease, while catastrophic events, such as stroke, heart attack, renal failure and dementia, are usually a result of a long period of uncontrolled HTN [9,10].

Hypertension has profound effects on the structure and function of the eye [11]. Retinal micro-vascular abnormalities such as arterial narrowing, arteriovenous nicking and retinopathy reflect the vascular damage from hypertension [12] & signifies current and past blood pressures which has progressed to a severe stage.¹³ As a result, presence of retinopathy may be an indication for initiating antihypertensive treatment, even in people with stage 1 hypertension (blood pressure, 140 to 159/90 to 99 mm Hg) who have no other evidence of target organ damage. Data suggest that the prevalence rates of various signs of retinopathy range from 2–15% in hypertensive adult though some authors says it is less than 1 % [11].

Left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) is a common finding in patients with fixed or borderline hypertension and can be diagnosed either by ECG or by echocardiography [14]. It is often thought to be a long-standing consequence of hypertension. However, some evidence suggests that increased LV mass precedes the onset of hypertension [15,16]. Data suggest, individuals with evidence of LVH have a 10-fold greater risk of developing cardiac failure than hypertensives without ECG evidence of LVH [17]. Besides this, echocardiographically-determined LV mass (LVM) indices, corrected for either body surface area or patients' height, are independent risk predictors of cardiovascular disease and chronic heart failure [9,18]. Hypertension and Microalbuminuria commonly coexist [19]. Microalbuminuria (MA) is defined as a slight elevation in urinary albumin excretion (UAE) above threshold and predicted cardiovascular morbidity and mortality independently [20,21]. The mechanism is controversial but is thought to be a renal manifestation of generalized vascular endothelial dysfunction and strongly linked with increased cardiovascular risk.²¹ Even though there are disparities between the various studies, the prevalence of microalbuminuria generally ranges between 20% and 30% in untreated hypertensive patients and is as high as 25% in patients undergoing anti-hypertensive treatment [21].

Overall prevalence of proteinuria is 9.7% and microalbuminuria is 19.1% in patient suffering from hypertensive kidney disease in Bangladesh [22].

The association between MA and hypertension & hypertension with LVH was described long time ago [9,15,16,21]. Relation of retinopathy and renal dysfunction with LVH in hypertensive patients or Vice

versa were also revealed in a few studies [23-25]. Some authors reports that LVH is an independent predictor for extra cardiac TODs in essential HTN and there is a significant association between different types of TOD in hypertensive populations [26]. Nevertheless, discordant conclusions on this matter emphasize the need for further investigation on such relationships [27]. Thus, this study was designed to assess the relation between hypertensive retinopathy with left ventricular hypertrophy and proteinuria in a tertiary care hospital of Bangladesh.

Materials and Methods

It was a cross-sectional observational study conducted in Department of Medicine and Department of Cardiology, Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH) in between July 2016 to June 2017. All patients who were admitted in Department of Medicine, and Cardiology with hypertension (systolic BP 140 or >140 mm Hg and diastolic BP 90 or >90 mm Hg) with retinopathy and other target organ damage were enrolled in the study. Total 384 patients were included of both sexes. Participants were properly informed about the nature of the study and consent obtained from those willing to participate. Detailed history including duration of hypertension, medications received, degree of control of hypertension and any history suggestive of adverse cardiac events along with prescribed medication were obtained. Thorough examination was done to evaluate presence of hypertension, evidence of hypertensive retinopathy, left ventricular hypertrophy and nephropathy. Blood pressure was recorded in sitting position in a bed by Auscultatory method with Sphygmomanometer (ALPK2, Japan) and stethoscope (Littman, Japan) in two settings at 15 min interval and classify according to NICE, 2011 guideline.

Degree of hypertensive retinopathy was assessed by direct ophthalmoscopic (HEINE, German) examination will be defined by Gunn and Keith, Barker and Wagener classification. Ophthalmoscope were done in a dark room, patient was sitted in a chair after 1% tropicamide eye drops given in each eye. After full dilation of pupil, right eye was examined by right eye and left eye was examined by left eye. During ophthalmoscope; optic media, optic disc, retinal blood vessels and retinal background were observed. Retinal findings were cross examined by an ophthalmologist in the department of Ophthalmology in DMCH.

M-mode, two dimensional echocardiography was performed for all study patients in the department of Cardiology in DMCH, in left partial decubitus position, using a HITACHI ALOKA ECHO machine (Model-F37, Hitachi Aloka Medical, China.) and a 2.5-3.5 MHz electrical transducer. End diastolic internal diameter (LVIDd), septal wall thickness (SWT) and posterior wall thickness (PWT) were calculated from the two dimensionally guided M-mode tracing and measured in

five consecutive cardiac cycle. LVH was defined as, when SWT is >11 mm and/or PWT is >11 mm in during diastole. Before echocardiography, ECG was done for each patient and find out ST segment and T-wave changes.

Spot urine sample was collected and perform ACR for proteinuria. Investigation were done to ascertain presence of microalbuminuria by spot urine sample examination for ACR (urinary albumin-creatinine ratio) in the department of Biochemistry in Banghabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) by Dimension Clinical Chemistry System (Particle-enhanced Turbidimetric Inhibition Immunoassay Method). Subjects were classified according to the ACR: <30 mg/g as normoalbuminuric, 30-300 mg/g as microalbuminuric and >300 mg/g as macroalbuminuric or overt proteinuria. Data were presented in tabulated form and were analyzed using computer based program Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for Windows version 23.

Observation and Results

The Cross-sectional observational study was carried out among 100 hypertensive adults with retinopathy in Department of Medicine & Cardiology, Dhaka Medical College Hospital for 1 years of period from July 2016 to June 2017.

Figure 1: Distribution of Patients in Different Age Groups (n=100)

Total 100 patients were studied. Minimum age was 29 and maximum age was 85 years. Mean age was 57.15 (±12.989) years. Most of the patients (27, 27%) were aged in between 56 to 65 years followed by 23 patients (23%) in between 46 to 55 years of age. Among rest 22 patients were from 66 to 75 years group, 14 patients were from group 36 – 45 years, 8 patients were from 76-85 and 6 patients were from group 26 to 35 years. See figure I for a column chart of the distribution.

Figure 2: Sex Distribution of Patients (n=100)

Among all the patients studied majority were male (61, 61%). 39 patients (39%) were females. A pie chart of sex distribution is shown in figure II.

Figure 3: Distribution of Patients According to History of Smoking (n= 100)

63 patients (63%) out of 100 were not smokers. 37patients (37%) had history of smoking. See figure VI for a pie chart.

Figure 4: Distribution of Patients According to BMI (n=100)

55% of the patients were over-weight. 21% were in the normal range of BMI and another 21% were in the obese range and the rest 3% were under-weight. Figure VII depicts the body built in the sample population of this study.

Figure 5: Distribution of Patients According to Duration of HTN (n=100)

Patients were inquired about the duration they had been suffering from hypertension. Majority of them (28%) were having HTN for less than 5 years. 26% diagnosed as hypertensive recently, 21% having HTN for 5-10 years, 16% had been suffering from HTN for more than 10 years and the rest 9% did not know the duration of being hypertensive. Figure VIII shows a column chart of the distribution.

Blood pressures of the study sample were measured and 57% were found having grade-1 hypertensive with mean systolic and diastolic BP 150.8 (± 5.4) mm Hg and 94 (± 2.6) mm Hg respectively. 30% were grade-2 and 13% were grade-3. Table I shows the distribution of grade of hypertension with mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure of each group.

Table 1: Severity of HTN with Mean Systolic and Diastolic Blood Pressure (n=100)

Severity of HTN	No. of patients	Mean ± SD systolic BP (mm Hg)	Mean ± SD diastolic BP (mm Hg)
Grade 1	57	150.8 ± 5.4	94.0 ± 2.6
Grade 2	30	170.3 ± 4.9	101.0 ± 4.7
Grade 3	13	188.0 ± 7.0	102.6 ± 6.5
Total	100	161.5 ± 14.5	97.2 ± 5.4

Figure 6: Distribution of Patients According to Antihypertensive Use (n=100)

Patients were asked about whether taking any medication and if any, how frequently. 23% were using no medication, 45% were on regular medication and the rest 32% were taking antihypertensive irregularly. See figure IX for a bar chart.

Figure 7: No. of Drugs Used by the Patients (n=100)

Patients were inquired about how many drugs they were taking for hypertension and asked to show the prescription as there are many combinations of drugs available in the local market of which they might be unaware. 36 patients were taking single antihypertensive drug, 30 patients on two drugs, 7 patients on three drugs and 4 patients on four drugs and 23 patients were taking no antihypertensive. See figure X for a column chart of the distribution.

Figure 8: Frequency of Grade of Retinopathy (n=100)

Grading of retinopathy was done according to Keith-Wagener-Barker Classification of hypertensive retinopathy and found 60% of the patients having grade-1 retinopathy. Grade-2 was in 16% patients, grade-3 in 20% and 4% patients were suffering from grade-4 retinopathy. Figure XI shows the frequency of severity of retinopathy with percentage in study sample.

There were significant positive associations between the severity of LVH on echocardiography and the mean systolic and diastolic BPs (both p-values < 0.01). Severity of LVH was higher in patients who have higher mean systolic blood pressure See table II for details.

Table 2: Association between Severity of HTN and LVH (n=100)

Severity of LVH on echocardiography	No. of patients	Mean ± SD systolic BP (mm Hg)	p-value for systolic BP	Mean ± SD diastolic BP (mm Hg)	p-value for diastolic BP
No LVH	53	154.2± 9.5	< 0.001	94.7±3.8	< 0.001
Mild LVH	23	166.4±13.9		100.6±6.0	
Moderate LVH	19	170.8±16.1		98.9±4.8	
Severe LVH	5	181.4±8.3		102.6±7.1	
Total	100	161.5±14.5		97.3±5.5	

Analysis was done by ANOVA and Spearman’s correlation

Table 3: Prevalence of Left Ventricular Hypertrophy on Electrocardiography in Different Classes of Left Ventricular Hypertrophy on Echocardiography (n=100)

Severity of LVH on echocardiography	LVH on ECG		No LVH on ECG		Total	p-value
	No.	%	No.	%		
No LVH	6	11.30	47	88.7	53	P < 0.001
Mild LVH	3	13.0	20	87.0	23	
Moderate LVH	12	63.2	7	36.8	19	
Severe LVH	3	60.00	2	40.00	5	
Total	24	24	76	76	100	

Out of 100 patients 53, 23, 19 and 5 patients had no, mild, moderate and severe LVH, respectively, on echocardiography. Among the 100 patients, only 24 (24%) showed characteristic features of LVH on ECG

(Table III). The relationship between echocardiographically-diagnosed and ECG-detected LVH was statistically significant (p < 0.001).

Table 4: Association between Severity of HTN and Severity of Proteinuria

Severity of HTN	Severity of Proteinuria			Total	Chi-square	p-value
	no proteinuria	micro albuminuria	overt proteinuria			
Grade 1	41 (71.90)	13 (22.80)	3 (5.30)	57	21.37	< 0.001
Grade 2	13 (43.30)	15 (50.00)	2 (6.70%)	30		
Grade 3	4(30.80)	4 (30.80)	5 (38.50)	13		
Total	58	32	10	100		

Proteinuria became significantly (p < 0.001) more obvious as the severity of HTN progressed. Details analysis is shown in table IV.

Table 5: Association between Hypertensive Retinopathy and LVH (n=100)

Grade of Retinopathy	LVH				OR (95% CI)	Chi-square	p-value
	yes	%	no	%			
Grade-1	24	40.0	36	60.0	1	3.50	0.32
Grade-2	9	56.2	7	43.8	1.929 (0.633-5.879)		
Grade-3	11	55.0	9	45.0	1.833 (0.660-5.090)		
Grade-4	3	75.0	1	25.0	4.5 (0.442-45.853)		

Patients who were with more severe retinopathy tended to have LVH; it was 4.5 times higher for patients with grade-4 hypertensive retinopathy (OR=4.5, 95% CI=0.442-45.853) relative to those with grade-1

retinopathy but there was no significant association between hypertensive retinopathy and LVH ($\chi^2 = 3.5, p = 0.32$). See table V for details.

Table 6: Association between Hypertensive Retinopathy and Proteinuria (n=100)

Grade of Retinopathy	Proteinuria				OR (95% CI)	Chi-square	p-value
	yes	%	no	%			
Grade-1	21	35.0	39	65.0	1	3.94	0.27
Grade-2	8	50.0	8	50.0	1.857 (0.609-5.66)		
Grade-3	10	50.0	10	50.0	1.857 (0.667-5.174)		
Grade-4	3	75.0	1	25.0	5.571 (0.545-56.95)		

The association of proteinuria with hypertensive retinopathy was not significant ($\chi^2 = 3.94, p = 0.27$). Compared to patients with stage-1 hypertensive retinopathy, those with stage 2, 3 and 4 hypertensive retinopathy were 1.857, 1.857 and 5.571 times more likely to have proteinuria respectively (95% CI= 0.609-5.66, 0.667-5.174, 0.545-56.95 respectively). Table VI gives the details of the analysis.

Discussion

This study was conducted in DMCH over a period of 1year duration. Total 100 patients of hypertensive retinopathy were taken for this study. Mean age was 57.15 (± 12.99) years with maximum and minimum age being 85 years and 29 years respectively. Majority of the patients (27%) were aged between 56 to 65 years. Hitha B et al [20] in their study entitled "Microalbuminuria in Patients with Essential Hypertension and its Relationship to Target Organ Damage: An Indian Experience" included 150 patients and found majority of the patients between 60 to 69 years of age. This finding corresponds with findings of present study indicating increased prevalence of hypertensive patients in older adults. In the search for prevalence of hypertension in Bangladesh Mohammad Abdul Baker Chowdhury and Colleagues found 19.1% hypertensive patients in between 60 to 69 years Chowdhury MAB et al [4] which supports the previous statement.

Majority of the study population was male (61%). Hitha B et al [20] also found a male majority in their study. Present study found 37% smokers in hypertensive patients (as illustrate in figure VI). Islam, S.M.S. et. Al

[22] in their study involving analysis of risk factors of hypertension found 23.4% smokers which is lower than the findings of present study.

In this study 86% patients had BMI more than normal (including 55% overweight and 21% obese patients) and 21% patients had normal weight (As illustrated in figure VII). Sheikh Mohammed Shariful Islam and colleagues found 36.4% overweight and 40.4% obese patients totaling 76.8% patients having more than normal BMI in Islam, S.M.S. et. Al [22]. This finding is similar to the observations of present study in that HTN is prevalent among patients having BMI more than 24. Majority of the patients had HTN (28%) for less than 5 years followed by 26% patients who were recently diagnosed and 21% patients having HTN for more than 5 years up to 10 years (As illustrated in figure VIII). Hitha, B. et. al. (2008) found majority of patients (27%) having HTN for less than 5 years. This nearly matches the findings of present study.

57% patients had grade 1, 30% patients had grade 2 and 13% patients had grade-3 hypertension (As illustrated in table I). Kabedi, N. N. et al [27] in their study entitled 'Hypertensive retinopathy and its association with cardiovascular, renal and cerebrovascular morbidity in Congolese patients' found grade 1, grade 2 and grade 3 hypertension in 30.2%, 21.4% and 48.4% patients respectively. This finding is different from present study.

Compliance to anti-hypertensive medication is a prerequisite for proper control of HTN. In the present study patients were asked about their practice of anti-hypertensive use. 45% patients were taking anti-

hypertensive regularly, 32% were taking anti-hypertensive irregularly and 23% patients were not taking any anti-hypertensive at all (As illustrated in figure IX). In comparison Hitha, B. et. Al [20] found respectively 35%, 33% and 31% patients taking antihypertensive nil, irregular and regularly.

36% patients were found to take single antihypertensive agent in this study. This is followed by 30% patients taking combination therapy of two drugs and 7% patients taking three drugs and 4% patients taking 4 drugs (As illustrated in figure X). A study conducted to find out antihypertensive prescription pattern by Hasan, M. J. found slightly different pattern of antihypertensive drug used in his study. He found 61.6% patients taking mono-therapy, 34.3% patients taking 2 drugs, 3% patients taking 3 drugs and 1% patients taking more than 3 drugs to control their hypertension. As the present study included hypertensive patients who have retinopathy, it is expected that there will be more user of combination therapy than monotherapy.

60% of total 100 patients had grade-1 retinopathy. Grade-2 was found in 16% patients, grade-3 in 20% and grade-4 retinopathy in 4% patients (As illustrated in figure XI). In Congolese study, Nelly N Kabedi and colleagues found respectively 13.3%, 22.8%, 11.8% and 6.2% patients having grade-1, grade-2, grade-3 and grade-4 retinopathy. Both these studies show that burden of retinopathy in hypertensive patients is mainly constituted by lower grade patients.

Significant positive association was found between severity of LVH and systolic and diastolic blood pressure (p value <0.001) (As illustrated in table II). This finding corresponds to the finding of Shirafkan, A. et al [9].

In this study [47, 26, 22 and 5] patients had no, mild, moderate and severe LVH, respectively, on echocardiography. On the other hand, only 29 patients (28.4%) showed characteristic features of LVH on ECG. Significantly more cases of LVH was detected in echocardiography than ECG (p value <0.001) (As illustrated in table III). This finding also conforms to the findings of Singaporean study Shirafkan, A. et al [9].

Patients with grade-4 retinopathy had 4.5 times more odds of finding echo or ECG evidence of LVH (OR=4.5, 95% CI=0.442-45.853) relative to those with grade-1 retinopathy. Whereas patients of grade-3 retinopathy had 1.8 times (OR=1.83, 95% CI 0.66-5.09) and grade-2 retinopathy had 1.9 times (OR 1.9, 95% CI 0.63- 5.87) more odds of having left ventricular hypertrophy. But, the association between retinopathy and left ventricular hypertrophy was not significant ($\chi^2 = 3.5, p = 0.32$) (As illustrated in table V). The Congolese study reported an increased odd of finding echo or ECG evidence of LVH in patients with increased grade of retinopathy. They also report non-significant

relationship between LVH and retinopathy in Kabedi, N. N. et al [27].

A significant positive association was found between severity of hypertension and severity of proteinuria ($\chi^2=21.37, p = <0.001$). But, association of hypertensive retinopathy and presence of proteinuria was not significant ($\chi^2 = 3.94, p = 0.27$) as illustrated in table VI. Though, patients with higher grade of retinopathy had higher odds of developing proteinuria. Omotoso, A. B. et al¹ in their study entitled 'Relationship between retinopathy and renal abnormalities in black hypertensive patients' also found a similar relationship between retinopathy and proteinuria.

Conclusion

Hypertension is a major preventable public health problem causing huge economic burden, loss of lives and economic loss as well. When more than one target organ damage occurs concurrently it makes the situation worse. In this study, relations between severity of Hypertension and Proteinuria and LVH was found but no significant relations were found between hypertensive retinopathy and LVH & proteinuria. However, in the absence of large randomized controlled trials, these findings must not be inferred to general population.

Limitations

- The study population was selected from medicine and cardiology department of a single tertiary level center in Dhaka city. So that the results of the study may not reflect the exact picture of the country
- The present study was conducted within a very short period of time.
- Small sample size was also a limitation of the present study. Therefore, in future further study may be undertaken with large sample size.
- It was a simple hospital based cross-sectional study. Prospective studies may reveal further information.

Conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest.

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Author Contributions

Study design and data analysis: Dr. Saad Ahmed Tanmoy

Data collection: Dr. Saad Ahmed Tanmoy

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